

Numerical Investigation of Non Fourier Heat Conduction in a Semi-infinite Body due to a Moving Concentrated Heat Source Composed with Radiational Boundary Condition

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Abstract—In this paper, the melting of a semi-infinite body as a result of a moving laser beam has been studied. Because the Fourier heat transfer equation at short times and large dimensions does not have sufficient accuracy; a non-Fourier form of heat transfer equation has been used. Due to the fact that the beam is moving in x direction, the temperature distribution and the melting pool shape are not asymmetric. As a result, the problem is a transient three-dimensional problem. Therefore, thermophysical properties such as heat conductivity coefficient, density and heat capacity are functions of temperature and material states. The enthalpy technique, used for the solution of phase change problems, has been used in an explicit finite volume form for the hyperbolic heat transfer equation. This technique has been used to calculate the transient temperature distribution in the semi-infinite body and the growth rate of the melt pool. In order to validate the numerical results, comparisons were made with experimental data. Finally, the results of this paper were compared with similar problem that has used the Fourier theory. The comparison shows the influence of infinite speed of heat propagation in Fourier theory on the temperature distribution and the melt pool size.

Keywords—Non-Fourier, Enthalpy technique, Melt pool, Radiational boundary condition

I. INTRODUCTION

INVESTIGATION of melting and solidification phenomena is important in most heat transfer engineering problems. For instance, in semiconductors producing technology, welding, found, crystallization and etc. The use of concentrated heat source energy such as laser and electrical discharge machining (EDM) are common nowadays in melting various materials. In all of problems like this, the solid and liquid phases are separated with an interface; interface developing in the solid or liquid phase, depends on both sides of the temperature gradients.

Rostami et al. [1] investigated the heating and melting of a semi-infinite body due to a stationary laser beam. Because the laser beam was stationary, the problem was assumed to be axisymmetric. The numerical solution was compared with experimental data and, because no vaporization occurred at

the surface of the workpiece, reasonable agreement was seen. Rostami and Raisi [2] studied the heating and melting of a semi-infinite body due to volumetric absorption of moving laser radiation. That was a transient three-dimensional conduction problem with a moving heat source and a moving phase boundary which was used with an explicit finite difference method. Temperature distribution and melt pool size for moving and a stationary laser beam were derived. In order to validate, the numerical solution was compared with experimental data. The comparisons showed that the numerical results were fairly accurate.

Sadd and Didlake [3] investigated the melting of a semi infinite solid in one dimensional based on non-Fourier heat conduction law postulated by Cattaneo [4] and Vernotte [5]. They confirmed that, unlike the classical Fourier theory which predicts an infinite speed of heat propagation, the non-Fourier theory implied that the speed of a thermal distribution is finite, and the effect of this finite thermal wave speed on the melting phenomenon was determined. Finally they found out that, non-Fourier results differ from the Fourier theory only for small values of time.

Fangming jiang [6] investigated experiments on porous material heated by a microsecond laser pulse and the corresponding theoretical analysis. Some non-Fourier heat conduction phenomena were observed in the experimental sample. The experimental results indicated that only if the thermal disturbance be strong enough (i.e., the pulse duration is short enough and the pulse heat flux is great enough) it is possible to observe apparent non-Fourier heat conduction phenomenon in the sample, and evident non-Fourier heat conduction phenomenon can only exist in a very limited region around the thermal disturbance position.

Abdel-jabbar et al. [7] investigated the thermal behavior of a thin slab under the effect of a fluctuating surface thermal disturbance, as described by the dual-phase-lag heat conduction model. It is found that, using the dual-phase-lag heat conduction model is essential at large frequencies of the surface disturbance. Mathematical criteria that specify the limits, beyond which both the hyperbolic wave and the dual-phase-lag heat conduction models deviate from the diffusion model, were obtained.

II. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

A review of literatures indicated that, all previous studied of the change-of-state heat transfer problems were based on

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the Fourier heat conduction law.

$$q = -k\nabla T \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) along with the conservation of energy gives the classical parabolic heat equation:

$$\alpha \nabla^2 T = \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

Many of the investigations indicated that Fourier's model possesses several serious shortcomings. The most prominent is that, this model implicates an infinite speed of heat propagation. Cattaneo and later Vernotte postulated a wave model for heat conduction in solids in the form below:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{q_x}{\tau} = -\frac{k}{\tau} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

The quantity τ is called the material thermal relaxation time and is a physical result of a finite thermal communication time between material points.

The conservation energy equation is given by:

$$q_x = q_{x+dx} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho c T) dV \quad (4)$$

Finally by using Cattaneo combination and conservation of energy equations, hyperbolic heat transfer equation may be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho c T)}{\partial t} + \tau \frac{\partial^2(\rho c T)}{\partial t^2} + V \frac{\partial(\rho c T)}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + g$$

The corresponding volumetric heat generation is given by [8]:

$$g = -\frac{dI_a}{dz} = \alpha I_s (1 - R) e^{-\alpha z} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the problem in the two-dimensional case

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of semi-infinite body. Profile of the beam is considered circular and elliptical. The intensity of the beam that has Gauss' distribution may be expressed as [9]:

$$I_s(x, y, t) = I_0 h(t) e^{-[(x^2+y^2)/w^2]} \quad (7)$$

$$I_s(x, y, t) = I_0 h(t) e^{-[(x/w_x)^2 + (y/w_y)^2]} \quad (8)$$

In last equations, w is the beam radius in the circular profile

state; w_x and w_y are the beam radius in the x and y directions in elliptical profile state. I_0 is the radiation intensity at the center of the beam, and $h(t)$ stands for the temporal variation of the intensity. In the case of continuous heat flux, $h(t)$ has the constant value of unity.

The local intensity of radiation decreases inside the material according to:

$$I_a = I_s (1 - R) e^{-\alpha z} \quad (9)$$

Where R is the surface reflectivity and α is the absorption coefficient of the material.

Eq. (5) must be solved for the solid and liquid phase separately. The two solutions should then be related via the energy boundary conditions at the solid-liquid interface. The dependence of the position of the interface on the temperature distribution makes the problem complicated. One way to avoid this complexity is to write the left side of Eq. (5) in terms of enthalpy:

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + \tau \frac{\partial^2 e}{\partial t^2} + V \frac{\partial e}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + g$$

In Eq. (10) e is term of enthalpy and may be expressed as:

$$e = \int \rho c dT \quad (11)$$

A. Initial and boundary condition

Initially, the temperature is equal to T_i everywhere:

$$\text{at } t=0 : \quad T=T_i \quad (12)$$

Initially, the temperature variation is equal to zero

$$\text{at } t=0 : \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The boundary condition at the surface may be expressed as:

$$\text{@ } z=0 : \quad -K \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \varepsilon(T) \sigma (T^4 - T_\infty^4) + h(T - T_\infty) \quad (14)$$

Regions far from the source are supposed to be uninfluenced by the source

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } x \rightarrow \pm\infty : \quad T &= T_i \\ \text{at } y \rightarrow \pm\infty : \quad T &= T_i \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

B. Conditions at the interface

The energy balance at the interface may be written as [9]:

Fig. 2 Solid-Liquid interface in a two-dimensional view.

$$\left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial X_s}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial X_s}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] \left[k_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial x} - k_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial x} \right] =$$

$$L \left(\tau \frac{\partial^2 X_s}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial X_s}{\partial t} - V \right)$$

$$\left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial Y_s}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial Y_s}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] \left[k_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial y} - k_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial y} \right] =$$

$$L \left(\tau \frac{\partial^2 Y_s}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial Y_s}{\partial t} \right)$$

$$\left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial Z_s}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial Z_s}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \left[k_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial z} - k_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial z} \right] =$$

$$L \left(\tau \frac{\partial^2 Z_s}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial Z_s}{\partial t} \right)$$

Where X_s, Y_s, Z_s indicate the coordinates of the interface in the x, y and z directions, also $\frac{\partial X_s}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial Y_s}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial Z_s}{\partial t}$ are the velocity components of the interface in the $x, y,$ and z directions, respectively. Once the enthalpy of each element is calculated, the following relations can be used to obtain the corresponding temperature [1]:

$$e_s = \int_{T_{ms}}^T \rho_s c_s dT \quad T_{ms} \leq T \quad (17)$$

$$e_l = \int_{T_{ml}}^T \rho_l c_l dT + L \quad T_{ml} \geq T$$

e_s, e_l are the amounts of the enthalpy in solid and liquid phases, respectively.

When an element contains both phases, x (i.e., the volume fraction of the liquid phase) must be calculated initially. The average enthalpy can be calculated afterward.

$$e = xe_l + (1-x)e_s \quad (18)$$

A procedure for the evaluation of the liquid fraction x will be introduced later.

For (ρc) an average value was assumed and by

substitution e_s, e_l from Eq. (17) in Eq. (18), Eq. (19) can be written as follow:

$$e = xL + (\rho c)_{av} (T - T_m) \quad (19)$$

Where, T_m is melt temperature.

C. Thermophysical properties

The thermophysical properties of the material were allowed to vary with temperature and phase state of the material. These properties for unalloyed aluminum may be expressed as [10, 11]:

C.1. Thermal conductivity coefficient K ($\frac{W}{m^2k}$)

$$\begin{aligned} K_s &= 226.67 + 0.033T & 300K < T < 400K \\ K_s &= 226.6 - 0.055T & 400K < T < 933K \\ K_s &= 63 + 0.03T & 933K < T < 1600K \\ (16) \quad K_s &= 114 & 1600K < T < 2723K \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

C.2. Specific heat at constant pressure C_p ($\frac{kJ}{kgk}$)

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ps} &= 0.762 + 4.67 \times 10^{-4}T & 300K < T < 933K \\ C_{pl} &= 0.921 & T > 933K \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

C.3. Density ρ ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$)

$$\rho_s = 2767 - 0.22T \quad 300K < T < 933K \quad (22)$$

C.4. Emissivity coefficient ϵ

$$\epsilon = 7.2 \times 10^{-5}T + 3.2 \times 10^{-3} \quad (23)$$

Also, latent heat of diffusion is equal to:

$$L = 3.95 \times 10^5 \quad \frac{J}{kg}$$

By using these equations, e_s, e_l may be expressed as two polynomial functions in order 3 and 2, respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} e_s &= 2108.454T + 0.5622T^2 - \\ & 3.4246 \times 10^{-5}T^3 - 2428827.8 \\ e_l &= 2431.44T + 0.12663T^2 + 9.4 \times 10^8 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$(\rho c)_{av}$ can be expressed as:

$$(\rho c)_{av} = x(\rho c)_l + (1-x)(\rho c)_s \quad (25)$$

Which $(\rho c)_s$ and $(\rho c)_l$ are related to solid and liquid states, respectively.
 By substituting Eq. (25) in Eq. (19), Eq. (19) can be written as follow:

$$e = xL + (3068.22 - 873.09x)(T - T_m) \quad (26)$$

In the numerical solution when an element contains only solid phase, the temperature can be calculated by applying the first term of Eq. (24), using the Newton-Raphson method. On the other hand, when an element contains only liquid phase, the temperature can be calculated by solution of polynomial function of order 2 in second term of Eq. (24). If an element contains two phases, Eq. (26) can be utilized to calculate the temperature.

III. NUMERICAL SOLUTION

In order to save computation time, the solution domain was divided into two regions: The inner region, which contains the liquid and/or solid state and the outer region, containing only the solid state. A fine mesh was used for the inner region, where the temperature gradients are large and the solid-liquid interface is present. The dimensions of the inner domain are smaller than outer region. On the basis of the work of Hsu and Mehrabian et al. [12] $I_0 w$ is an important parameter. If $I_0 w < 1 \times 10^6$, the maximum temperature in the workpiece will not reach the boiling point of aluminum. Under this condition the maximum diameter of the melt pool is approximately $2.4w$ and depth of melt pool is nearly w for a stationary beam.

In numerical solutions often beam radius is considered about $100 \mu m$. Based on these arguments, the diameter of the inner region will be 240 microns (μm). But because of moving heat source it was chosen to be 300 microns. The outer boundary of the computation domain was chosen such that conditions at infinity could be applied. The outer region radius usually is considered as 20 times of the beam radius. Then for a beam with a radius of $100 \mu m$ the R_o can be calculated as follow:

$$R_o = 20 \times w = 2000 \mu m \quad (27)$$

For determining the number of grids in the inner region, the grid study was used. First, the temperature of central point of body geometry versus the grid numbers was drawn. The results showed that temperature changing in 15th grid and higher can be assumed uniform and can be neglected. As a result, the grid numbers in inner region were considered as 15×15 .

Fig. 3 Temperature variation of the surface central point versus number of the nodes

Grid numbers in z direction is considered as 13. Hence:

$$\Delta x_i = \Delta y_i = \frac{300}{15} = 20 \mu m, \quad \Delta z_i = 12 \mu m$$

Each 5 internal grids are equivalent to one external grid. Therefore:

$$\Delta x_o = \Delta y_o = 5 \times \Delta x_i = 100 \mu m, \quad \Delta z_o = 5 \times \Delta z_i = 60 \mu m$$

Finally, $(15 \times 15 \times 13 = 2925)$ rectangular grids were used for the inner region, and 57127 grids for outer region.

Fig. 4 Grid generation in x-y and x-z planes

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In numerical solution of Eq. (10) in explicit finite volume form, the beam intensity was $I_0 = 3.5 \times 10^9 (W / m^2)$, the target velocity $V_w / 2\alpha = 0.45$, relaxation time $\tau = 0.2 \times 10^{-14}$ sec [13] and the beam radius was $100 \mu m$. A pulse duration of $t_p = 1ms$ was used and initial temperature was $300K$.

Fig. 5 shows the maximum depth of the melt pool as a function of the beam intensity. It is assumed that the surface absorbs all of the beam energy. As it can be seen from Fig. 5, the numerical analysis is in good agreement with the experimental data, for low beam intensity. However, in the wake of the reaching to the vaporization threshold, the numerical analysis and experimental data are becoming further from each other.

Fig. 6 shows the depth of the melt pool as a function of the radius distance from the center of the beam. In this Fig., it can be seen that, there is negligible difference between numerical analysis and experimental data.

The temperature distribution of the center point as a function of time at various velocities is shown in Fig. 7. As it is observed, as much as the velocity of the beam increases, the temperature of the point decreases. This phenomenon is observed, due to the fact that as much as the velocity increases, the amount of energy that the specific point observes decreases.

Fig. 8 shows the diameter of the melt pool along x direction at $z=0$. It can be seen that, as much as the velocity of the beam increases, the diameter of the melt pool along x direction increases slightly. On the other hand, by increasing the velocity of the beam, the diameter of the melt pool along y direction decreases.

The solid-liquid boundary of the melt pool in the xy plane for $Vw/2\alpha = 0.45$ is shown in Fig. 9. It can be perceived from Fig. 9 that, because of the moving beam, the melt pool tends to the right. Also, as time passes, the diameter of the melt pool increases and eventually it reaches to a specific value.

Fig. 10 shows the solid-liquid boundary of the melt pool in xz plane for $Vw/2\alpha = 0.3$. Due to the moving beam, the melt pool tends to the right. Fig. 11 shows the isotherm in xy plane for specific time and beam intensity, but for various beam velocity. The temperature fields are not symmetric due to the moving laser beam. It can be observed that, the temperature curves are more intensive at the left of the x direction.

Fig. 12 shows the isotherm in the xy plane when the elliptic beam is used. The diameter of the melt pool along x and y directions are shown in Fig. 13, by using the elliptic beam.

Now, we are comparing the result of this paper and another paper, which has used Fourier model.

Fig. 14 shows the temperature of the center point. It can be perceived from Fig. 13 that, the temperature of the center point increases faster, when the Fourier model is employed. But, the Fourier model and hyperbolic model reach each other by passing the time. This result was predictable, because the fourier and the hyperbolic models differ just in short times.

Fig. 15 shows the depth of the melt pool as a function of time for a dimensionless velocity (translational speed) of $Vw/2\alpha = 0.45$. As it can be observed from Fig. 15, in comparison to the other case, the melt pool is deeper when Fourier heat conduction is applied. Also, the diameter of the melt pool along x direction at $z=0$ for dimensionless velocity $Vw/2\alpha = 0.45$, is shown in Fig. 16. It can be seen from this Fig. that, the diameter of the melt pool along x direction, using Fourier model, can increase faster and finally it reaches to a specific value.

The solid-liquid boundary in xy plane at $\frac{t}{t_p} = 0.5$ for

$Vw/2\alpha = 0.45$ is shown in Fig. 17. As it can be predicted from Fig. 16, the size of the melt pool in xy plane when Fourier model is used, is greater than when the hyperbolic model is used. Fig. 18 shows the solid-liquid boundary of the melt pool

in xz plane at $\frac{t}{t_p} = 0.5$ for $Vw/2\alpha = 0.45$. According to Fig. 18 it can be concluded that, using Fourier model, the size of the melt pool in xz plane is greater than the same melt pool obtained from the hyperbolic model.

Fig. 5 Melting pool depth versus laser beam intensity at the center.

Fig. 6 Melting pool depth versus radial distance from the laser beam center

Fig. 7 Surface center point temperature with respect to the time at various speeds and intensity of $I_0 = 3.5 \times 10^9 \text{ (W/m}^2\text{)}$ in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 8 Melting pool diameter on the x-axis with respect to the time for two different speeds in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 9 Melting pool image on the x-y plane at a constant velocity and different times for a circular laser beam in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 10 Melting pool image on the x-z plane at a constant velocity and different times for a circular laser beam in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 11 Temperature contours in the x-y plane for circular laser beam in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 12 Temperature contours in the x-y plane for elliptical laser beam in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 13 Melting pool diameter on the x and y axes versus time for elliptical laser beam in continuous heat flux case

Fig. 14 Surface central point temperature versus time using Fourier and Hyperbolic methods

Fig. 17 Melting pool image on the x-y plane for a circular laser beam using Fourier and Hyperbolic methods

Fig. 15 Melting pool depth variation with time using Fourier and Hyperbolic methods

Fig. 18 Melting pool image on the x-z plane for a circular laser beam using Fourier and Hyperbolic methods

Fig. 16 Melting pool diameter on the x-axis versus time using Fourier and Hyperbolic methods

V. CONCLUSION

The temperature distribution and the size of the melt pool for an aluminum solid under the laser beam were studied. The hyperbolic heat equation was applied. The results of the hyperbolic model and the fourier model were compared and it was seen that the increment of the melt pool and temperature fields were slower, when the hyperbolic model was applied. This phenomenon is in the wake of the infinite speed of the thermal waves in fourier model. Also it was deduced that, the hyperbolic heat conduction model is suitable for short times and large domains and it can reached to the accurate results.

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